

ATRIUM – Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities

Work Package WP6
Service Interoperability and EOSC Integration

Milestone 7
Interim assessment on Service Interoperability and EOSC Integration

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List of Abbreviations

ACDH	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities
ADS	Archaeology Data Service
API	Application Programming Interface
ARCHE	A Resource Centre for the HumanitiEs
ATRIUM	Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire (European Organization for Nuclear Research)
DOG	Digital Object Gateway
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OSCARS	Open Science Clusters' Action for Research & Science
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report describes the progress made within the ATRIUM Work Package 6 during the first 21 months of the project. Consisting of 4 tasks related to service interoperability and integration with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), substantial steps were taken towards the implementation of the final results, scheduled for month 42 of the project (June 2027). In this first period, no major obstacles were identified.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document reports on the progress within the tasks of ATRIUM WP6 during the first 21 months of the project.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 to 5 describe the state of affairs in the respective 4 tasks of Work Package 6. For each of these tasks first the achievements up to September 2025 are listed. Then a subsection summarizes the plans for the remaining 21 months. At the end of the document, the intermediary conclusions are drawn.

2. Service Interoperability (T6.1)

2.1 Achievements so far

In the first year, the Digital Object Gateway (DOG) saw several updates to the backend ([DogLib](#)) and the frontend ([DogApp](#)). Besides these updates, the use case of [support](#) for the ADS repository was addressed by investigating the available APIs and finally resolving the implementation of an HTML parser to retrieve the relevant metadata

fields. This use case was finally tested by selecting a PDF from an ADS landing page and processing it via the Language Resource Switchboard.

During 2025, the DOG back-end was re-engineered to rely on a more robust parsing of JSON files and to include initial support for FAIR signposting.

As far as GoTriple is concerned, the aim of improving interoperability between services clashed with some limitations of its API implementation when ATRIUM started. The Net7 team therefore worked to improve the REST APIs of the services by:

- enhancing response times
- adding the possibility to find documents by their persistent identifiers (DOIs in particular).

The latter improvement was also made possible by the work done in Task 3.2 (Catalogue Harmonisation), aimed at improving GoTriple's metadata quality, in particular through better management of persistent identifiers for documents (DOI, Handle.net, ISBN, ISSN). Finally, integration of GoTriple with the Digital Object Gateway was proposed and implemented in the [DOG beta environment](#). As GoTriple does not associate a DOI or a Handle with its documents, the implementation choice was based on the URLs of the platform's content.

2.2 Plans for the remaining period

The supported list of repositories by the DOG will be extended. A [longlist](#) of candidates is kept, from which in close coordination with the work package a shortlist will be created which will then lead to implementation and testing.

At the side of the user front-end, an option will be added to call the Language Resource Switchboard after selecting a specific file.

As far as GoTriple is concerned, Net7 is planning to revise the APIs to improve semantic support. The endpoints of /documents and /documents/{id} already support content negotiation to produce output in JSON-LD format using the TRIPLE Ontology. As the refinement of this ontology continues in ATRIUM (Task T3.1: Semantic Interoperability), Net7 plans to revise the APIs to fully support the changes in the ontology for the aforementioned endpoints and to add JSON-LD support for the other search APIs (/authors, /authors/{id}, /projects, /projects/{id}).

3. Connecting national repositories to Episciences (T6.2)

3.1 Achievements so far

During this reporting period, the focus of T 6.2 was to establish a workflow for onboarding of new sources to Episciences. ACDH ARCHE (A Resource Centre for the HumanitiEs) was chosen as a first use case for this integration. A mapping of data schemas was created and ARCHE is available as a data source for Episciences on a development instance. Pending further testing, this integration can be deployed to the main instance.

While technical interoperability using OAI-PMH protocol could be established easily, some conceptual/methodical challenges were identified regarding the review of datasets as opposed to traditional publications. Regarding the publication type, it was decided to use the datasets themselves as publications, rather than papers based on datasets. This allows a more comprehensive use of research data repositories, such as ARCHE, as a datasource for Episciences and contributes to promoting datasets as independent research outputs.

3.2 Plans for the remaining period

Using the experience gained in this reporting period, future activities will focus on the integration of new repositories to Episciences. One of the sources for candidates for this integration process will be the DARIAH tools and services catalogue, which lists repositories relevant for the DARIAH community. The timeline and the final list of repositories to be connected will be subject to agreements between DARIAH, Episciences and various DARIAH partner institutions.

4. EOSC: community integration and evaluation (T6.3)

4.1 Achievements so far

In light of the significant transition and transformation period of the EOSC ecosystem in 2024 (including the conclusion of the EOSC Future project, the procurement of core services and the establishment of the EOSC EU node), the focus of T6.3 was initially on compiling a portfolio of relevant tools and services for the ATRIUM project and publishing it on the SSH Open Marketplace – a catalogue of tools and methods pertinent to the SSH community within the broader EOSC ecosystem. This approach enables the reuse of the detailed data model, facilitates collaborative curation and editorial practices within the Marketplace, and contributes to a shared knowledge base for the entire SSH community. At the same time, the portfolio is dynamically mirrored on the [ATRIUM website](#).

Following the launch of the EOSC EU Node and the initiation of the EOSC Federation¹ T6.3 began exploring how and under what conditions the [offered services](#) could be used. To this end, a set of diverse use cases or scenarios is being compiled, with a primary focus on the implementation of ATRIUM workflows and demonstrators (WP4 and WP5). One common scenario in certain humanities disciplines is the datafication, enrichment and analysis of (historical) text-based data. In practice, this is a whole complex solution space with many variables with respect to the sources and type of input data (manuscripts, newspapers, correspondence, language variation across time and genres, etc.) and the methods and corresponding tools that can be applied. Some of these were implemented in tasks 4.1 and 4.2.

Besides the activities in the ATRIUM project, tangents to other infrastructure projects were explored, especially OSCARS and ECHOES, to identify synergies and potential for reuse.

An important milestone and synchronisation point in this respect was the [OSCARS composability & AAI workshop](#) held at CERN in Geneva from September 17th to 19th, which focused on composability and interoperability of services and solutions for scientific workflows in the context of EOSC. One of the scenarios in OSCARS, proposed by the SSH cluster is a more specialised variant of the general scenario for text-based data, focusing on datafication, enrichment and analysis of digitised historical newspapers, with a clear potential for reuse of tools and workflows delivered in ATRIUM.

¹ EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

4.2 Plans for the remaining period

The next step will be to refine and finalise the use case definitions, detailing the concrete workflows, the potential datasets and data sources, as well as a set of tools and requirements. These will serve as a specification for the implementation on the existing cloud infrastructures. While the primary focus is on EOSC and the EOSC EU Node, alternative solutions, like the [Galaxy platform](#) will be explored to arrive at a broader picture of the possibilities. An important aspect of this task is the critical evaluation of the feasibility and usability of cloud-based workflows and the identification of potential pitfalls.

5. Connecting the oral history transcription portal to the EOSC (T6.4)

5.1 Achievements so far

A fully functional [development version](#) of the Transcription Portal, with support for Dutch, English, German and Italian was launched and connected to the [beta instance](#) of the Language Resource Switchboard. Experimental versions of related services (machine translation, automatic summarisation, speaker diarization) have been developed in parallel, to integrate these into the transcription portal and/or the Switchboard and to gather feedback from the user community. Various approaches for Speaker diarisation services have been explored.

5.2 Plans for the remaining period

We will further explore new techniques to improve speaker diarisation, and fine tune the text processing modules for summarisation and translation. We have planned a [Research Forum](#) with WP7 on 25th November 2025 in Munich. Suggestions from that event will be used for further improvement of the Transcription Portal.

Consortium

Research Infrastructures

Beneficiaries

Affiliated Entities

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